

LIESEGANG RING FORMATION OF THE SPARINGLY SOLUBLE SALTS OF RARER ELEMENTS IN GELATIN

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Phenomenon of the periodic structures was first observed and studied by Liesegang (*Naturwiss.*, 1896, 11, 353; *Phot. Archiv*, 1896, 221). Large number of periodic structures were also obtained by Hausmann (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1904, 40, 110), Stansfield (*Amer. J. Sci.*, 1917, 43, 1), Hatschek (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1912, 10, 77), Orlovski (*Kolloid Z.*, 1926, 39, 48), Kuzmenko (*Ukraine Chem. J.*, 1928, 3, 231), Daus and Tower (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 6.5), Dhar and Chatterji (*ibid.*, 1924, 28, 41) and Mukherjee and Chatterji (*Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 50, 147). The periodic structures described by Liesegang were those in which rings were separated by clear spaces, but Dhar and Chatterji (*loc. cit.*) have established that there are two types of banded structures, in one type, rings are separated by clear spaces while in the other the precipitate is separated by a band of peptised sol. In this connection they have prepared many rings of various sparingly soluble salts of Ag, Cu, Pb, Hg, Zn, Ni, Co, etc., but the study on the ring formation of the rarer elements has not yet been done. Therefore a systematic study of the sparingly soluble salts of rarer elements has been undertaken.

The experimental work has been done on the same lines that of Dhar and Chatterji (*loc. cit.*).

1% Normal solution of sodium tungstate, selenious acid, sodium selenate, sodium ortho- and metavanadate, potassium tellurate, thorium nitrate, zirconium nitrate, thallic sulphate, cerous nitrate, ceric nitrate and beryllium nitrate were evenly distributed in 5% gelatin. Above solutions were poured in three different series of test tubes and allowed to set. 20, 10, and 5% of the respective precipitating salts were allowed to diffuse from the top of the test tubes. But in the case of uranyl compounds, 20, 10 and 5% of uranyl nitrate were allowed to diffuse in the test tubes from the top containing 1% of the precipitating electrolytes uniformly distributed immediately in 5% gelatin solution as on following the usual procedure, the gel sets. The results obtained are given below.

TABLE I

Type I (rings separated by clear spaces).	Type II (precipitate separated by a band of peptised sol).
(1) Tungstates of Sr, Ba and Cd	Tungstate of Cr
(2) Selenite of Cu	Selenium metal: acid reduced by SnCl ₂ & NH ₄ OH.HCl
(3) Selenium metal: acid reduced by FeSO ₄	—
(4) Selenate of Ba	Vanadate (ortho) of Cu, Pb and Cr
(5) Vanadate (ortho) of Ca	Vanadate (meta) of Ba, Be and U
(6) Vanadate (meta) of Cd	

TABLE I (contd.)

Type I.	Type II.
(7) Tellurates of Ag, Cd and Pb	Tellurate of Fe (ous)
(8) Thorium salts : thorium hydroxide, oxalate, sulphate, iodate, fluoride and ferrocyanide	—
(9) Zirconium phosphate	Zirconium hydroxide
(10) Thallium salts : oxalate and hydroxide	Thallium salts : iodide and sulphide
(11) Cerous salts : oxalate and carbonate	—
(12) Ceric hydroxide	—
(13) Uranyl compounds : uranyl oxalate, ammonium phosphate and ferrocyanide	Sodium uranate
(14) Beryllium carbonate	Beryllium hydroxide

For the following salts no rings could be obtained: vanadate of Sr, Ag and Fe (ous), uranyl sulphide and ammonium uranate.

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